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Identifying the Median Grade-Tonnage Curve from the Global Database of VMS Copper Mining Projects

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Abstract

This paper presents a statistical analysis of the global database of Volcanogenic Massive Sulphide (VMS) mineral deposits. The paper shows the joint and partial probability distributions for copper equivalent grade and total tonnage based on current metals prices for copper, zinc, lead, and gold. The article develops a new method using the joint distribution to identify the set of quantile values for grade and tonnage that have approximately 50% probability; this set of quantile values represents the median grade-tonnage curve for VMS deposits around the world. The article also shows how to analyze individual projects in comparison with the global database. For example, the size of the Shamlugskoe mine in Armenia is ranked according to the global database. For another example, a model of the exploration project called Mount Sicker is presented and compared to nearby projects that are in the global database.

Keywords: Natural Resources, Mining, Copper, Zinc, Volcanogenic Massive Sulphide, Metals Grade, Deposit Tonnage, Grade-Tonnage Curve, Probability Distribution, Median Path, Statistical Analysis, Simulation, Quantile

JEL Codes:

A19 - Other	H25 - Business Taxes and Subsidies
B59 - Other (120)	K2 - Regulation and Business Law
C0 - General	K23 - Regulated Industries
C02 - Mathematical Methods	L2 - Firm Objectives, Organization,
C14 - Nonparametric Methods	L5 - Regulation and Industrial Policy
C15 - Statistical Simulation Methods	L7 - Industry Studies: Primary Products
C18 - Methodological Issues: General	L72 - Mining, Extraction, and Refining
C4 - Econometric and Statistical Methods	Q3 - Nonrenewable Resources and
C40 - General	Q32 - Exhaustible Resources
C6 - Mathematical Methods...	Q33 - Resource Booms
C63 - Computational Techniques	Q5 - Environmental Economics
C69 - Other	Y1 - Data: Tables and Charts
C81 - Methodology for Microeconomic Data	
D2 - Production and Organizations	
D81 - Criteria for Decision-Making Risk	
G17 - Financial Forecasting and Simulation	
G31 - Capital Budgeting	

Identifying the Median Grade-Tonnage Curve from the Global Database of VMS Copper Mining Projects

This paper presents a statistical analysis of the global database of Volcanogenic Massive Sulphide (VMS) mineral deposits. The paper shows the joint and partial probability distributions for copper equivalent grade and total tonnage based on current metals prices for copper, zinc, lead, and gold. The article develops a new method to use the joint distribution to identify the set of quantile values for grade and tonnage that have approximately 50% probability; this set of quantile values represents the median grade-tonnage curve for VMS deposits around the world. The article also shows how to analyze individual projects in comparison with the global database. For example, the size of the Shamlugskoe mine in Armenia is ranked according to the global database. For another example, an exploration project called Mount Sicker is presented and compared to nearby projects that are in the global database.

The USGS database (Mosier, Berger, & Singer, 2009) provides a comprehensive basis for research. For example, Bell (2025a) focuses on the distribution of gross metal value. We can expand the analysis in several ways. For example, we can identify a subset of the global database that are currently mines or were operating mines before. How many of the USGS global databases for VMS were ever mined? Do we have data on historical production for global VMS deposits? The exploration side of the mining business uses a hypothetical valuation of potential deposit size, but operating mines have real financial information that can be used to model the mine value (Bell, 2018a, 2018b, 2018c). It is possible to estimate the costs for mining development and operation at each deposit around the world based on the project-specific capital and operating requirements, but this information is not available in the USGS database because many deposits do not have current estimates of mineral resources or mine plans.

Statistical Distributions for VMS Deposits Around the World

The spatial extent of the orebody in the ground characterizes each mineral deposit, but there is a complicated relationship between the shape of the orebody and the assumptions about how to mine it and process it. There are a lot of parameters to model the range of possible outcomes for the economic performance of a mine, but a basic concept is the grade-tonnage curve. Each deposit has a grade-tonnage curve that shows how the total tonnage and average grade change together depending on other assumptions, like cutoff grade. Each deposit has a range of values for the grade-tonnage data pair.

It is also possible to show the grade-tonnage curve for all deposits in the world, as in Figure 1, where each data point represents one project. By comparing projects, Figure 1 does not show anything about the potential grade-tonnage tradeoff for each project. However, Figure 1 is useful for understanding broad patterns in global data for this deposit type in terms of the joint distribution for grade and tonnage based on a logarithmic transformation of the tonnage data. Figures 2 and 3 provide further descriptive statistics in terms of partial distribution for grade and tonnage. Each of these three distributions shows extreme fat tails.

Figure 1: Grade-Tonnage Data for all VMS Deposits from the USGS

Scatterplot of USGS Global Data for all VMS Deposits

Figure 2: Partial Distribution Function for all VMS with Copper Grade

Distribution for all VMS around the world (N=868)

Figure 3: Partial Distribution Function for all VMS with Tonnage

Distribution for all VMS around the world (N=868)

To calculate the copper equivalent grade, I use the following assumptions for the metals prices: copper \$10,000 per tonne, zinc \$3,000 per tonne, lead \$2,000 per tonne, and gold \$200 per gram. The copper equivalent grade is calculated as a weighted average of metal grade using these prices as the weights. Tables 1, 2, and 3 provide summary statistics for all the VMS deposits based on the copper equivalent grade. For example, Table 1 shows how many deposits are in each grade range.

Table 1: Number of VMS around the world based on intervals for copper grade

Number of VMS Deposits	Total: 646 (% Copper Equivalent)	
	Lower Grade	Upper Grade
28	1	2
34	2	3
45	3	4
70	4	5
132	5	6
209	6	7
129	7	12

Table 2: Grade-Tonnage Statistics for VMS by grade intervals

Lower Grade	Upper Grade	Average Grade	Average Tonnage
1%	2%	2%	16,210,916
2%	3%	3%	13,785,124
3%	4%	4%	7,155,841
4%	5%	5%	7,176,143
5%	6%	6%	5,717,111
6%	7%	7%	2,986,471
7%	12%	12%	2,148,214

Table 3: Grade-Tonnage Statistics for VMS by grade intervals

Lower Grade	Upper Grade	Average Grade	Std. Deviation Grade	Average Tonnage	Std. Deviation Tonnage
1	2	1.8%	14%	16,210,916	46,530,779
2	3	2.5%	31%	13,785,124	33,267,609
3	4	3.5%	29%	7,155,841	13,744,639
4	5	4.5%	28%	7,176,143	17,843,679
5	6	5.5%	31%	5,717,111	9,868,523
6	7	6.4%	24%	2,986,471	4,093,711
7	12	8.8%	130%	2,148,214	5,460,619

The global distribution of deposit tonnage for specific grades provides a way to compare one deposit to others. If you have a deposit with specific grade-tonnage, then you can rank it relative to global data. Or if you have a target grade, then you can identify the likely amount of tonnage. For example, Table 2 shows the average tonnage is 16 million tonnes (Mt) for a deposit with a copper-equivalent grade of 1-2% Cu; however, Table 3 shows that there is a very large variability for such projects based on the standard deviation in tonnage of 46Mt.

Figures 4 and 5 provide a pair of charts that work together to show how to make predictions about typical project parameters based on the global dataset. Figure 4 shows the grade-tonnage curve for all projects without applying a log-transform to the tonnage data. Figure 4 shows the extreme fat tails in grade and tonnage, as also shown in the partial distribution in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 5 shows the typical tonnage for each interval of copper grade, plus an estimate of the upper range for tonnage by adding one standard deviation. Figure 5 shows the information presented in Table 3. Whereas Bell (2025a) focuses on the distribution of gross metal value alone, this article shows the insights available by analyzing grade and tonnage separately.

Figure 4: Examples of Grade-Tonnage Curve for all VMS Deposits around the world

Scatterplot of all VMS data for Grade-Tonnage

Figure 5: Range of Values for Tonnage of VMS clustered by Grade

Grade-Tonnage Statistics for VMS by grade intervals

Further statistical analysis of the global database allows us to compare specific projects to the global inventory. For example, we can use quantiles to check if a particular deposit ranks high or low relative to the global database. Table 4 shows the result of these calculations using the grade intervals for the tables and figures above, where the lower grade is the quantile and the result is the percentage of all projects with a lower grade (percentile of cumulative distribution). For example, there are zero deposits in the global database with less than 1% copper-equivalent grade, whereas 96% of all projects have a grade less than 7% copper-equivalent. Figure 6 shows these results.

Table 4: Ranking Deposit Grade versus all VMS Deposits

Lower Grade (Quantile)	Percentile of USGS Data
1%	0%
2%	19%
3%	49%
4%	74%
5%	84%
6%	91%
7%	96%

Figure 6: Calculate Quantiles based on all VMS Deposits

Quantiles from USGS Database of all VMS

Median Grade-Tonnage Curve: All Deposits at 50th Percentile from the VMS Database

Further statistical analysis of the joint distribution for grade and tonnage together allows insight into projects around the world. For example, we can estimate the median grade-tonnage curve, where each data point represents a deposit that is at the 50th percentile; each deposit on this curve represents a typical deposit in terms of grade-tonnage pair. This exploratory data analysis exercise is possible because the probability function for the grade-tonnage curve has two dimensions, which allows a tradeoff between grade and tonnage without changing the percentile. When we increase tonnage, there are more projects that are smaller; however, we can simultaneously decrease the grade to decrease the number of projects that are smaller. The net effect cancels out and keeps the percentile constant. To estimate the median grade-tonnage curve, we start by picking a value for the grade-tonnage pair and then calculate how many deposits have a smaller grade **and** tonnage (care is required to estimate the joint probability function in an empirical setting to ensure the methods accurately count the “and” condition).

The 50th percentile is defined in terms of the joint cumulative distribution function. There is not just one single project with a 50th percentile, but many combinations of value for grade and tonnage that give 50th percentile. We can identify a set of all quantiles where the joint probability is 50th percentile based on the following equation:

Equation 1:

$$\{Q_T, Q_G \mid 0.5-\epsilon < \text{Probability}(\text{Tonnes} < QT ; \text{Grade} < QG) < 0.5+\epsilon \}$$

The set of quantiles $\{Q_T, Q_G\}$ defines the median grade-tonnage curve. The parameter epsilon ϵ takes a small value to ensure that the quantiles are not a null set: for the empirical results in Table 5, ϵ approximately equal to 1/646, so the results include one value for each grade-tonnage pair around the quantile that corresponds to the 50th percentile. Table 5 shows several stylized features. Above 4-5% copper grade, the average tonnage is consistently around 3Mt. For a 2-3% copper grade, average tonnage varies widely from 10 to +40Mt. As in Table 3, these patterns reflect the relative frequency for each cluster: there are many low-grade deposits, and they have a wide range of tonnages, but only a few high-grade deposits, and they have a smaller range of tonnage.

Table 5: Median Deposit as all Grade-Tonnage Pairs at 50th Percentile

Copper Grade (% Cu Eq)	2.0%	2.5%	3.0%	3.5%	4.0%	4.5%	5.0%	5.5%	6.0%	6.5%	7.0%	7.5%	8.0%
Tonnage (Mt)	--	--	43	13	6	5	4	3	3	2	2	2	2

Table 6 provides an empirical estimate of the joint cumulative distribution function itself for the entire database. The red entries show low probabilities, green show high, and the white range in the middle shows the median grade-tonnage pairs around the 50th percentile.

Table 6: Joint Probabilities for Copper Grade (horizontal) and Tonnage (vertical)

	1.0%	1.5%	2.0%	2.5%	3.0%	3.5%	4.0%	4.5%	5.0%	5.5%	6.0%	6.5%	7.0%	7.5%	8.0%
1	4%	9%	14%	18%	23%	25%	28%	29%	31%	32%	33%	34%	35%	35%	35%
2	5%	12%	19%	25%	31%	35%	38%	39%	41%	43%	44%	46%	47%	47%	47%
3	6%	14%	22%	29%	35%	40%	44%	46%	48%	50%	51%	53%	54%	54%	55%
4	6%	16%	24%	31%	38%	44%	48%	50%	53%	55%	57%	59%	60%	60%	60%
5	6%	16%	26%	34%	41%	47%	52%	54%	58%	60%	62%	64%	65%	65%	65%
6	6%	17%	27%	35%	43%	49%	54%	57%	60%	63%	65%	66%	68%	68%	68%
7	7%	18%	28%	36%	44%	51%	56%	58%	62%	64%	66%	68%	70%	70%	70%
8	7%	18%	29%	37%	46%	52%	57%	60%	63%	66%	68%	70%	71%	72%	72%
9	7%	18%	29%	38%	47%	53%	58%	61%	65%	67%	69%	71%	73%	73%	73%
10	7%	18%	29%	38%	47%	54%	60%	62%	66%	68%	70%	73%	74%	74%	75%
11	7%	19%	30%	39%	49%	55%	61%	64%	68%	70%	72%	74%	76%	76%	76%
12	7%	19%	31%	40%	50%	57%	62%	65%	69%	71%	74%	76%	77%	78%	78%
13	8%	20%	32%	41%	51%	58%	63%	66%	70%	72%	75%	77%	78%	79%	79%
14	8%	20%	32%	41%	51%	58%	64%	67%	71%	73%	75%	77%	79%	79%	79%
15	8%	20%	32%	42%	52%	59%	65%	68%	72%	74%	76%	79%	80%	80%	81%
16	8%	20%	32%	42%	52%	59%	65%	68%	73%	75%	77%	79%	81%	81%	81%
17	8%	20%	33%	43%	53%	60%	66%	69%	73%	75%	78%	80%	81%	82%	82%
18	8%	20%	33%	43%	53%	60%	66%	69%	74%	76%	78%	80%	82%	82%	82%
19	8%	20%	33%	43%	53%	60%	66%	70%	74%	76%	78%	81%	82%	82%	83%

...
39	9%	22%	37%	48%	58%	66%	73%	76%	81%	83%	86%	88%	90%	90%	91%
40	9%	23%	37%	48%	58%	66%	73%	76%	81%	84%	86%	88%	90%	90%	91%
41	9%	23%	37%	48%	59%	67%	73%	77%	81%	84%	86%	89%	90%	90%	91%
42	9%	23%	37%	48%	59%	67%	73%	77%	81%	84%	86%	89%	90%	90%	91%
43	9%	23%	37%	48%	59%	67%	74%	77%	81%	84%	87%	89%	90%	91%	91%

Note that the joint probability function is largely the same for tonnage greater than 20M, so Table 6 truncates the results and jumps to 40Mt. It is possible to use a heat map for three-dimensional visualization of results across a broader range of values for grade-tonnage. It is also possible to repeat the empirical calculations with greater resolution for the grade-tonnage grid of values, such as increasing tonnage by 0.1Mt rather than 1Mt and grade by 0.1% rather than 1%. However, the results in Table 6 show a smooth surface where the median grade-tonnage curve takes the values as in Table 5.

Grade-Tonnage Curves based on the Geology of the Mineral Deposit

Each deposit has a grade-tonnage curve by itself, but these curves are not included in the USGS database. One way to estimate the grade-tonnage curve for a deposit is by changing the cutoff grade, say from 0.1% to 0.5% copper. As the cutoff grade changes, the average grade and the total tonnage change. If the cutoff grade is high enough, then there will not be any ore left. Performing these calculations requires that we have a geological model for the mineral deposit and specialized computer software, which looks like the video game Minecraft, as shown in Figures 6 and 7.

The way we visualize a mineral deposit is essential to understand it accurately. Cowan (2014) shows how the drillhole intercepts on a deposit can either be unrecognizable or clearly match a typical deposit model, depending on the orientation of the viewing angle in three dimensions. Figure 6 from Cowan, as below, presents two views of an orebody with four colour-coded categories representing gold grade. The diagrams in Figure 6 show that if the cutoff grade is zero, then the entire orebody in the diagram is included, and the entire coloured shape defines the total tonnage. If we increase the cutoff grade, then the lower-grade ore is excluded, and the total tonnage decreases. The exact amounts are not provided in the article, but the diagrams provide enough information to guesstimate the grade-tonnage curve for this individual deposit as follows.

Figure 6: Views of Hypothetical Ore Body in Open Pit Mine Plan from Cowan (2014)

Figure 7: Comparison of Mine Plan Visualization and the Minecraft video game

It is possible to estimate the shape of the deposit in Figure 6 because it is clearly a very large open-pit mine. I assume it has a depth of 400 metres and a radius of 300 metres for a total volume of 37.7 million cubic metres or 102 million tonnes. I assume the total ore body is approximately 10% of the total pit at a 0 g/t Au cutoff, which is 10Mt. I assume the average grade of the deposit at a 0 g/t Au cutoff is 1.5 g/t Au, which yields a total gold content of 15 million grams or approximately 500,000 ounces of gold. At a gold price of \$200 per gram, this is a gross metal value of approximately \$3 billion. As an open-pit mine, the unit costs for mining could be as low as \$20 per tonne or \$2 billion total to remove all 100Mt of rock. In this case, the mine would yield a total gross metal value larger than the cost of mining; the mine would have potential for an operating profit, but the details would depend on the cost of processing the ore.

As we change the cutoff grade for the geological model for the deposit in Figure 6, we can trace out the grade-tonnage curve. I assume the lowest cutoff grade 0 g/t Au corresponds to 100% of the ore body size, the 1 g/t Au cutoff corresponds to around 80% of the ore body, the 2 g/t Au cutoff corresponds to around 20% of ore body, and the 3 g/t Au cutoff corresponds to around 2% of the ore body. Based on further assumptions for the average grade depending on the cutoff grade provided in Table 7, we can estimate the grade-tonnage curve for this project under these highly simplified assumptions. We can also show the corresponding gross metal value for each grade-tonnage data pair.

Table 7: Hypothetical Grade-Tonnage Curve for Deposit in Figure from Cowan (2014)

Cutoff Grade (g/t Au)	Tonnage	Average Grade (g/t Au)	Gross Metal Value (\$200 / gram Au)
0	10,000,000	1.5	\$3 billion
1	8,000,000	2.5	\$4 billion
2	2,000,000	3.5	\$1.4 billion
3	200,000	4	\$0.16 billion

The way the gross metal value changes for each version of the ore body in Table 7 reflects a stylized feature of mine plan optimization (Bell, 2025c). The lowest cutoff grade generates a large gross metal value, but the value can actually be increased at a higher cutoff grade. Not all mineralized material is economic.

Furthermore, assuming the total mining costs are constant at \$2 billion as above (\$20 per tonne times 100Mt) allows us to determine if the mine produces more gold than it costs to operate. It is important to note, however, that the gross metal value is not necessarily equal to the revenue for the mine because the gross metal value represents the theoretical value of gold contained in unprocessed ore. If the mine sells the ore as a concentrate, then it will capture a fraction (maybe around 50%) of gross metal value. If the mine processes the ore, then it will capture a higher fraction (maybe as much as 100%), but it will incur additional costs to build the capital assets to process and refine the raw ore into finished metal.

Another way to estimate a grade-tonnage curve is by changing which parts of the mineral deposit are included in the mine plan. Again, this requires a geological model to estimate tradeoffs. We can start with a geological model that includes all mineralization and then consider what a deposit looks like if it has the highest average grade possible. Or what if it has the lowest average grade possible? This approach starts with the target value for the average grade and then calculates the mine plan based on different assumptions about which parts of the deposit are included to search for examples of total tonnage to yield that target grade. The grade-tonnage curve is a flexible concept that can be used in a variety of ways.

Analysis of the Shamlugskoe VMS Deposit in Armenia

This section shows how to compare data from one specific deposit to the global database. I randomly picked a project called Shamlugskoe in Armenia. The USGS database mentions that it was founded in 1741 and started mining in 1770, but does not say when mining stopped. Based on satellite views, the Shamlugskoe appears to be still active today.

Figure 8 shows the Shamlugskoe mine and another nearby as they appear today. These are examples of VMS deposits in the USGS global database that were recently in production, and these operating mines provide useful examples for how the VMS deposits around the world are being mined today. What are the operating constraints on these mines today? How does the current production rate compare with historical activity going back to the 1700s? Are we digging an open-pit down through the old historical underground mine workings? How do the different generations of mining overlap and interact for a project like this with such a history?

The USGS database does not have data for the grade or tonnage of the Shamlugskoe deposit, but the commentary section does mention research written in Russian in the 1970s and 1980s that describes: “*Reserve: 0.25 million t Cu. 70 economic ore bodies of pipes, concordant lenses ≤70 m long and 10 m wide, disseminated-veined zones. Jurassic-Cretaceous Somkheto-Karabakh volcanic island arc. 165 MYA.*” Another estimate for the Shamlugskoe deposit from 2009 on Mindat describes it as 4.5 Mt at 3.54% Cu, 1.71% Pb, 4.96% Zn, 8.1 g/t Ag and 1.7 Mt @ 0.7 g/t Au; the copper equivalent grade is approximately 5.5% Cu based on current prices.

What is the gross metal value today of that historical copper reserve? At copper prices above \$10,000 per tonne and reserves of 250,000 tonnes of copper, the total gross metal value is over \$2.5 billion. The USGS database does not give information about the grade-tonnage curve for the deposit. How does tonnage change with different cutoff grades? What is the highest possible grade before the tonnage goes to zero? What is the total tonnage as the average grade goes to zero? We can consider these different scenarios using a geological model of the deposit to generate a bottom-up approach to understanding the deposit.

We can also compare the deposit to global data using a top-down approach. How does the Shamlugskoe deposit at 5Mt at 5.5% copper equivalent compare with the global distribution for VMS deposits? Figures 9 and 10 below show the cohort of all VMS deposits with copper grade between 4.5% and 5.5%. Figure 9 shows there are some very large deposits with +40Mt and 4.825% copper equivalent grade. The average tonnage is 5Mt for all 63 deposits in this grade range. This Shamlugskoe deposit itself has 5 Mt tonnage, which suggests that it is of average size for similar VMS deposits around the world. Figures 9 and 10 show the distribution of tonnage for all VMS with less than 4.5% to 5.5% copper equivalent grade as a peer group for the Shamlugskoe deposit. There are 63 other VMS deposits around the world with similar grades.

Figure 8: Google Earth views of the Shamlugskoe and Teghut Mines in Armenia

Figure 9: Tonnage Data for all VMS with Copper Grades 4.5-5.5%

Figure 10: Cumulative Distribution Function for all deposits with 4.5-5.5% Copper

What if the Shamlugskoe deposit had a lower grade? Figure 11 shows the grade-tonnage distribution for VMS with a grade below 1.5% copper equivalent. The average from Figure 11 is 1% copper equivalent and 15.8 million tonnes, which I use as a data point for a hypothetical grade-tonnage curve for this deposit.

Figure 11: Grade-Tonnage Curve for the Largest VMS around the world

Grade-Tonnage Curve for all VMS with less than 1.5% Cu Eq

Based on the calculation in Figure 11 and assumptions for the tonnage with higher grades, I estimate the grade-tonnage curve for the Shamlugskoe deposit as in Table 8 and Figure 12 below.

Table 8: Hypothetical Grade-Tonnage Curve for Shamlugskoe Deposit

Cutoff Grade (% Cu Eq)	Tonnage	Average Grade
0	20,000,000	1.8%
1	15,800,000	2.5%
2	12,000,000	3.5%
3	10,00,000	4.5%
4	8,000,000	5.5%
5	5,000,000	6.4%
6	3,000,000	8.8%

Figure 12: Assumed values for Grade-Tonnage Curve

Assumption for Shamlugskoe VMS Deposit

To further analyze the grade-tonnage curve for this deposit versus the global database, Table 9 shows several calculations based on different scenarios. Each scenario corresponds to a different point on the grade-tonnage curve assumed in Table 8 and Figure 12.

Table 9: Probabilities for Shamlugskoe Grade-Tonnage Assumptions

Scenario	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Tonnage	20,000,000	15,800,000	12,000,000	10,000,000	8,000,000	5,000,000	3,000,000
Grade (% Cu Eq)	1.8%	2.5%	3.5%	4.5%	5.5%	6.4%	8.8%
Percentile (Grade)	7%	27%	46%	58%	65%	69%	73%
Percentile (Tonnage)	65%	63%	60%	58%	56%	51%	42%
Joint Percentile (Independent)	5%	17%	28%	34%	36%	35%	31%
Joint Percentile (Empirical)	36%	56%	76%	84%	88%	85%	75%

In Table 9, the grade-tonnage assumptions are written in italics. The results are to be interpreted as follows. The “Percentile (Grade)” represents the partial cumulative distribution function: the proportion of all VMS deposits that have a smaller grade. The “Percentile (Tonnage)” represents the proportion of all VMS that have smaller tonnage. The “Joint Percentile (Independent)” is calculated as the Percentile (Grade) multiplied by the Percentile (Tonnage), which is the correct value if the two variables are independent. The “Joint Percentile (Empirical)” is calculated as the proportion of all VMS deposits that have a smaller grade **and** tonnage.

The scénario (A) assumes 20Mt tonnage and 1.8% copper equivalent grade. The percentile for grade shows that 7% of all VMS have a lower grade than 1.8%. The percentile for tonnage shows that 65% of all VMS have tonnage lower than 20Mt. If the two variables are independent, then the joint result would indicate that only 5% of all projects have less than 20Mt tonnage at 1.8% copper grade. However, the empirical version of the joint distribution shows that 36% of all projects have a smaller grade and tonnage. These results show that scénario (A) is much more likely than expected after accounting for the statistical relationship between tonnage and grade: scénario (A) has an unusually small grade-tonnage assuming the variables are independent, but is much less unusual based on real data from the global database.

By repeating this exercise for all scenarios, we see there are substantial differences between the estimates of the joint probabilities based on empirical data versus the theoretical assumption that the variables are independent. For example, Scénario (E) assumes 8 Mt at 5.5% copper equivalent, and the results show that 88% of all VMS deposits have smaller grade and tonnage, which suggests it is an unusually large and rich deposit. In contrast, the percentiles for Scénario (E) assuming independence show 36% of all deposits have a smaller grade and tonnage, which suggests it is an unusually small and poor deposit. This is a big difference driven by the complicated statistical relationship between grade and tonnage.

Figure 13 below shows the location of the Shamlugskoe deposit at 41°10'14.5"N 44°43'31.2"E. It also shows the extent of surface disturbance from mining covering a distance of approximately 1.2 km, up to 400 metres wide. The underground mining development at the site is unknown. In order for the deposit to contain 5Mt with 5% copper as above, it requires approximately 2 million cubic metres of space, which can be contained in a shape with 1,000 metres strike length, 400 metres vertical dip, and 5 metres width. This is useful as a toy model for the geometry of the deposit, although reality is more complicated.

It is possible to overlay the dimensions of another orebody at the Shamlugskoe site to understand the potential mineral endowment here better. This kind of comparison is a bottom-up way to compare the deposit to other VMS based on the actual geology of other deposits, which is similar to the top-down comparison for total grade-tonnage as described throughout this article. When transposing other mines onto this site, it becomes apparent how mining can have a large impact on the local environment.

Figure 13: View of the Shamlugskoe deposit showing 1.2km strike length

The EcoLur Network (2025) writes:

Shamlukh Mine Caused Disastrous Conditions to the Environment: Under EcoLur’s Ecological Risk Model, the mine hazard category is 3, i.e. caused disastrous conditions to human health and the environment due to the excessive concentrations of copper, lead, zinc and sulphur. Under the official information provided by the Energy and Natural Resources Ministry, as of 01.07.2013, the right to soil management of Shamlukh copper mine for mining has been issued to “Akhtala Ore Dressing Combine” CJSC.

The disastrous pollution impact from Shamlugskoe can be fixed. The history of this mine reportedly dates back to the 1700s, yet it still appears to be active today. This project presents opportunities to do new things in old places. Is it a potential source for critical minerals? Or does the cleanup of the historical pollution at the site provide new economic opportunities? Could new infrastructure change the economics of the mine and give it new life? There are many ways for strategic investment to clean up old problems and avoid new ones. These kinds of deposits with such ancient mining history deserve tremendous support and investment into all aspects of economic development from public and private players; the longer the history of the mine, the greater potential size for the Tragedy Of The Commons that accrued during all operations.

Analysis of Surface Showings at Mount Sicker Copper Project

An exploration-stage mining project has substantial uncertainty about the deposit size and economics, such that companies pay to acquire information about the project's potential (Bell, 2015). For example, the Mount Sicker project (Bell, 2025b) is at the early stages of exploration, where results comprise surface sampling that shows a highlight interval of 250 metres at +8% Copper. What is the likely mineral endowment at this site? Can we use a bottom-up approach to estimate the prospective geological units and metal content, or a top-down approach to see where it ranks in the global distribution of deposits?

Figure 14: Distribution for Surface Samples with 250 metres at 8% copper at Mount Sicker

One way to model the deposits is to assume the grade-tonnage, then infer the shape of the deposit. For example, a 5Mt deposit is composed of 1km strike length with a 500m and 4m wide target zone. How do those dimensions compare with results from the site? This is shown in Figure 15 below. This approach can be further extended by taking deposits from other locations and overlaying them at this site. For example, take the Shamlugskoe mine from Armenia and compare it with the results at Mount Sicker, as in Figure 16 below. This kind of overlay does not show where the orebody is hiding at Mount Sicker, but it does show what kind of space is required to contain the target deposit.

What if the Mount Sicker deposit area contains 5Mt at 5 Mt at 5% copper, similar to Shamlugskoe? Methods from this paper are used to represent the median grade-tonnage curve from global data as a top-down approach. Geological constraints based on local conditions as a bottom-up approach. Possible to meet in the middle. For example, take different values for average tonnage and plot at the Mount Sicker project: does it have space to host that amount of tonnage? Simplifying assumptions about the geometry of the orebody.

Figure 15: Example of a 1-kilometre strike in red line and a 250m highlight in pink

Figure 16: Overlay of Shamlugskoe at Mount Sicker

In addition, Table 10 provides the summary statistics for two deposits in the USGS database that are located immediately adjacent to the Mount Sicker project. These deposits provide a close comparison for local conditions to estimate the potential size of a new deposit at Mount Sicker.

Table 10: Grade-Tonnage and Gross Metal Value for Adjacent Deposits

Deposit Name	Tonnage (Mt)	Grade (% Cu Eq.)	Gross Metal Value	Percentile (Gross Metal Value)	Percentile (Grade and Tonnage)
Lara	1.87	1.96	\$367,791,600	46%	18%
Lenora-Twin J	0.6	3.68	\$220,800,000	37%	21%

Table 10 shows the grade-tonnage data, the gross metal value, and two versions of the percentile rankings for the deposits. The percentile for gross metal value is determined by comparing the gross metal value for each deposit to all others in the database. The Lara is a mid-range project based on the 46th percentile whereas the Lenora is relatively small at the 37th percentile. These results may reflect how the Lenora deposit was previously mined and the current tonnage estimate does not include ore that was removed by old timers. Also, The percentile for grade and tonnage is calculated using the joint distribution by counting how many deposits around the world have smaller grade and smaller tonnage than the project. The Lara is the 18th percentile, which reflects the fact that it has relatively small tonnage (less than 2Mt) for the relatively low grade (less than 2% copper equivalent). The Lenora is also relatively small at the 21st percentile, which reflects the small tonnage (0.6Mt) and higher grade (3.6% copper equivalent). Would any new discoveries in this area look similar to these other known deposits? Does the historical data accurately represent the grade-tonnage for these other known deposits?

One way to expand this analysis is to identify clusters of VMS deposits that occur close to each other and compare them to other clusters. Is there evidence that some clusters of deposits have relatively higher grade-tonnage than other clusters, which could be driven by more productive local conditions for the generation of this type of deposit?

There are several confounding factors for using other deposits as a way to provide guidance. For one, the total size of deposits is a function of historical spending and does not necessarily reflect true mineral endowment. Exploration could have stopped when the company ran out of money, not when they exhausted the potential deposit. For another, the VMS deposits occur in clusters, and the distribution of grade-tonnage within a cluster allows for relatively larger deposits to be hidden in the area. Productive camps still yield discoveries of new deposits and productive deposits can still yield discoveries of new ore zones.

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